

143. Tracking the innovation-decision process of early adopters of field robots in sugar beet production

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Abstract

Understanding how farmers make decisions about new sustainable technologies is essential for wider adoption. This study examined Bavarian farmers ($n=41$) that are early adopters of the Farmdroid FD20, a robot for sowing and hoeing, by applying Rogers' five-stage innovation-decision process. The results show that 93% of the surveyed FD20 users are involved in organic farming, mainly sugar beet (98%). These early adopters are mostly well educated, interested in technology, pragmatic and satisfied with the performance and benefits of the innovation. The relatively high adoption rate highlights the promising potential of robots to support organic farming practices in Bavaria.

Keywords: diffusion of innovations, early adopters, innovation-decision process, online survey, robot

Introduction

In recent years, a growing number of agricultural machinery companies and startups have developed autonomous field robots, yet market penetration remains slow and limited to specific applications. The motivation to automate tasks such as seeding, fertilising, and weed management is clear: autonomous systems could not only replace (lacking) manual labour within current farming systems (Rial-Lovera, 2018) but may also help reduce environmental impacts and enable the development of new cultivation methods (Lowenberg-DeBoer *et al.*, 2021). Despite the apparent advantages, field robots are not yet widely used across Europe. However, some solutions, such as the autonomous sowing and hoeing robot FD20 by the Danish company Farmdroid, have the potential to replace manual labour, reduce environmental impacts, and change work organisation. According to the manufacturer, 500 units will be in use across Europe and abroad by the end of 2024 (Farmdroid, 2024). Since 2019, this robot qualifies for funding under the Bavarian Special Agricultural Program (BaySL Digital), which provides a 40% investment support for automation technology for weed control, including field robots. The FD20 is suitable for use in row crops such as sugar beet and vegetables as it can manage weeds also within rows thanks to storing the GNSS coordinates of sown plants. This makes the robot particularly interesting for organic farming. Two studies conducted in Germany indicate that application in organic farming and labour reduction are key drivers of increased investment interest in field robots (Rübecke von Veltheim and Heise, 2021; Spykman *et al.*, 2021). Other stakeholders in the agricultural sector (e.g., technology manufacturers, researchers, and advisors) identified the limited availability and high cost of manual labour as primary motivators for investing in robots (Rial-Lovera, 2018; Rübecke von Veltheim *et al.*, 2020).

Understanding the decision and implementation processes of farmers associated with these technologies is crucial for forecasting the technology's market diffusion. Based on the empirical results of an online survey of Bavarian farmers and first-time users of the FD20, the five-stage Innovation-Decision process established by Rogers (2003) is traced, and the special nature of the early adopters is carved out. Early adopters, according to Rogers' *Diffusion of Innovations* theory, are individuals or groups who adopt new technologies or innovations shortly after the 'innovators', who are also characterised as first users of technologies in the prototype stage. Early adopters make up approximately 13.5% of the population on Rogers' adoption curve and are characterised by their

openness to new ideas, social influence, and their key role of bridging the preceding innovators and the subsequent rest of a potential target population (Rogers, 2003). They help validate a technology and thus build trust. By exclusively surveying the defined group of early adopters of the market-ready FD20, it is possible to simulate the Innovation–Decision process and derive indications for better market penetration of autonomous field robots for various applications.

Material and methods

The survey was aimed at early adopters of the FD20 in Bavaria. The German federal state of Bavaria runs an investment support program (BaySL Digital) that grants various rates of investment support for digital agricultural technologies. The sub-section ‘Digital Hoeing and Crop Protection Technology’ was launched in October 2019 and also applies to weeding robots such as the Farmdroid FD20. During the first funding period (October 2019–December 2022) 90 funding applications for robots were submitted and approved by December 2022, 88 of which for the FD20. Not all approved applications resulted in purchases of the robot. Farmers, who bought the robot and received the investment support reimbursement, concomitantly agreed to be contacted for evaluation in the future. Based on these funding guidelines, the population of 64 actual recipients of investment support for the FD20 in Bavaria were contacted for participation in a standardized online survey in February 2024. The questionnaire included questions regarding farm and respondent profiles along with their experience using the FD20 for at least one full growing season. The survey items were developed based on a literature review and insights from a preliminary focus group discussion with a small group of early adopters of the FD20 (Spykman *et al.*, 2023). Survey participants were asked about their motivations for purchasing the FD20, its acquisition process, its use across different crops, and its economic impacts. Of the 64 contacted farm managers, 41 completed the survey, yielding a response rate of 66%.

The experiences stated by these early adopters were analysed within the framework of Rogers’ Diffusion of Innovations theory, with a particular focus on the five-stage Innovation–Decision process: starting with ‘knowledge’ and ‘persuasion’ of a technology, follow by the actual ‘decision’ and its ‘implementation’ and finally a ‘confirmation’ stage (Figure 1). All stages are impacted by communication channels, which can take on different roles along the (social) process to create or change attitudes. Rogers assigns these to two main categories: mass media (e.g., TV, newspaper, trade journals) and interpersonal channels. Detailed characteristics of the five stages are explained in the ‘Results and Discussion’ section contextualized by the survey results.

Results and Discussion

Sample characteristics and use of the robot

The survey results indicate that the FD20 is predominantly used in organic farming operations (93%), almost always for sugar beet cultivation (98%). In 2023, the average area covered by the FD20 was 14 ha, aligning with the economically viable range for hoeing operations for this robot (Handler *et al.*, 2024; Spykman and Gabriel, 2023). On average, the FD20 was used on 4.7 fields per farm, requiring nearly 44 km of logistical travel per robot and farm per year, or 3.1 km/ha per year. The robot required an average of 5.6 h/ha per year for sowing and 25.4 h for hoeing. Additionally, the farmer spent 5.3 labour hours on preparation, calibration, logistics, and troubleshooting. These times also affect labour dynamics, reducing seasonal labour needs for weed management from 4.6 to 3.7 workers on average. It is difficult to ascertain whether this decline can be attributed solely to the use of a robot. However, a trend towards a reduction in manual seasonal labour is to be expected. Yet, 54% of the farm managers surveyed reported an increase in personal time spent on weed management, suggesting a shift from manual labour to technical and organisational tasks. In addition, the learning process was very time-consuming for half of the respondents.

Figure 1. Model of the Innovation-Decision process (retrieved from Rogers, 2003, p.170; copyright © 2003 by The Free Press, a division of Simon & Schuster).

Tracing the Innovation-Decision process

(1) Knowledge stage: The Innovation-Decision process starts with the knowledge stage, which distinguishes between three types of knowledge: awareness-knowledge (knowledge of innovation's existence), how-to-know knowledge (how to use technology correctly) and principal knowledge about functionality of an innovation (Rogers, 2003). While the latter is assumed as a basic requirement for farmers to consider the utilisation of automatic sowing and hoeing technology in general, it is important for the potential user of such complex systems become aware of the technology and comprehend its usability in the first place. A keyword search of “field robots” of three major trade journals read by farmers in southern Germany shows that the number of detailed print and online articles reporting about field robots increased continuously and nearly doubled between 2019 and 2023, up to 40 articles per year. Critical reporting on the constraints of digital technologies has also increased in the period from 2014 to 2018 compared to 2008 and 2013. It can be assumed that this media presence will reinforce awareness and principal knowledge just as much as robot demonstration events and technology trade fairs. Knowledge about the functionality and ‘how to use’ the robots can also be acquired on these occasions to a limited extent. While agronomic capacities are partly taken over by the machine, information technology knowledge must be expanded for the use of robots (Waltmann *et al.*, 2019). As the driver is no longer sitting on the machine, preparation and control of the robot requires relearning. This learning is supported by a certain amount of prior training, but also by the mindset and accessibility to technical subjects of the user. The present online survey of the early adopters in Bavaria demonstrates that these are farmers with a strong pioneer spirit, which is typical for those who embrace innovations (Rogers, 2003). In 92% of the cases, the operations manager was also the person responsible for robot operations. More than 70% of the FD20 users surveyed were under 50 years of age (official statistics: 44% of farm managers are under 54 years; Destatis, 2021a,b). Also, the number of higher professional qualification is on a significantly higher level than the average population: 30% of them with a university degree, 11% agricultural technicians and 27% agricultural master craftsmen (Destatis, 2021a: 25% in total). The prerequisites for a rapid acquisition of the necessary knowledge skills are good for organic sugar beet farmers in Bavaria.

(2) Persuasion stage: in this second stage, an individual forms a favourable or unfavourable attitude toward an innovation. In contrast to the previous knowledge-centred stage, the persuasion stage is seen as more affect-determined (Rogers, 2003). Affection is steered by uncertainty about the functions and effects of the new technology but can also be influenced by the reinforcement of the social environment (e.g., peers, colleagues). Individuals actively seek information that is credible to them, and often rely on a trustworthy social environment to do so. While selective information on the innovation is collected from scientific sources, peers' subjective experiences and opinions are more accessible and convincing for farmers who are interested in a robot. One reason for this is that peers have the same motives for switching to autonomous processes. The survey of FD20 users in Bavaria revealed that compensating for the shortage of seasonal labour was the main motive (Table 1). Similarly, soil protection is a decisive factor. The lower pressure due to the lighter robots compared to tractors is particularly a target in scientific research (Calleja-Huerta, 2023). Government funding and an interest in using technical innovations on their own farms also play important roles for many farmers: Over half of the participants see these aspects as strongly motivating to invest in robots. The latter is also evident for some of the respondents, who see their pioneering spirit as an important incentive to purchase the robot (39% state this as a 'strong motive').

According to Rogers (2003) the persuasion stage is also affected by the perceived characteristics of the innovation. He argued that innovations offering more relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity (as opposed to complex technologies), trialability, and observability will be adopted faster than other innovations. Kuehne *et al.* (2017) generated the ADOPT tool to record the factors influencing the innovation diffusion process and to forecast technology market diffusion. In addition to assessing the peak adoption rate in a specific user population, this model also calculates the time until this maximum is reached. Factors that promote the learning ability of a technology in relation to the perception of real benefits ("degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than the idea it superseded"; Rogers, 2003: p.229) have a particular impact on the diffusion time period. If the FD20 is seen as a complex and disruptive technology for organic sugar beet production, which is difficult to trial and can only be observed in rare situations, a rapid diffusion of the technology seems unlikely. The high level of interest in the technology and the pioneering spirit of the early adopters in Bavaria, however, suggest the opposite

(3) Decision stage: At this stage of the innovation-decision process, the potential user chooses to adopt or reject an innovation. A decision to adopt does not prevent discontinuance in later stages of the process ('passive rejection'). The option to test a technology on small-scale trial basis in the previous stage of the process can help speed up the decision and better cope with uncertainty about an innovation's 'consequences' (Rogers, 2003). The survey of the Bavarian early adopters reveals that partial trialling was not possible as with other technical innovations (e.g. trialling a new variety in one field). 81% of survey participants bought the robot for their individual farm rather than as

Table 1. Motives and expectations for the persuasion to invest in the FD20

Motivation	Strong	Light	No
Lack of availability of seasonal labour	68%	22%	10%
Soil protection (lighter equipment)	63%	29%	7%
Public funding	56%	39%	5%
Interest in technology	56%	37%	7%
Poor quality of manual work	46%	32%	22%
Pioneer spirit	39%	49%	12%

Source: FD20 farmer survey 2024 (N=41).

a tenancy in common or part of a machinery group to spread the risk. . However, the decision-making process benefits from the option of ‘trial by others’, in which demonstration and field trial opportunities provided by ‘change agents’ help familiarise peer groups with the technology. This is exemplified by the extensive FD20 sales network in southern Germany, but also the availability of demonstration events by independent extension and research organisations.

(4) Implementation stage: At this stage, an innovation is put into practice, although uncertainty about the outcomes of the innovation can still pose a challenge. Therefore, the adopter may require technical support from change agents and others to help reduce uncertainty regarding its potential consequences. The survey showed that the dealer and sales network continue to be the most important partner for obtaining information on serious problems. 95% of users turn to their dealer, 37% turn to other farmers who use the FD20. Only 20% enquire directly with the manufacturer in Denmark. According to Rogers (2003), the extent to which users modify an innovation after implementation, known as ‘re-invention’, is another indicator for a successful implementation and enhances the potential for the innovation’s sustainability. In total, 37% of the survey respondents have already made modifications to the robot or the attached tools themselves. Hereby, mainly the hoeing units on the FD20 were modified (67%), but there were also adjustments to the energy supply (40%) or the sowing units and seed tanks (33%). This high level of re-invention shows that early adopters with a strong interest in technology and distinct pioneering spirit can flexibly deal with any technical deficits or locational disadvantages. It is evidence of the personal involvement of farmers with the new technology, which makes likely the continuity of use.

(5) Confirmation stage: “At the confirmation stage, the individual seeks reinforcement for the innovation-decision already made [...]” (Rogers, 2003: p. 189). Although users would revise their decision if they were exposed to conflicting messages about the innovation, they still look to prevent or at least reduce the state of dissonance when it occurs. Users will evaluate whether the technology fulfils or even exceeds the original expectations. The surveyed farm managers had between one to three sugar beet seasons of experience with the robot. When asked directly, 83% agreed strongly or slightly that using the FD20 met their expectations for reducing manual labour hours (Table 2). However, over half of the respondents (54%) noted that the person responsible for weed management faces increased time requirements compared to the period prior to robot use, suggesting a shift from manual tasks to technical and organisational work (Rübcke von Veltheim and Heise, 2021). For about half of respondents, the learning curve for using the robot on their farm was manageable, and 44% found that external support (e.g., from dealers, manufacturers, or technical advisors) required for setup was minimal. Asked for an overall assessment, 20 of the 41 respondents were satisfied with the robot’s weed control, though results varied by year and weather. Eleven participants found the outcomes acceptable, ten gave no specific judgement or indicated changing results.

Table 2. Experiences with the implementation of the FD20.

	Strongly agree	Slightly agree	Un-decided	Slightly disagree	Strongly disagree
Savings in manual labour	56%	27%	5%	12%	0%
Now higher effort in weed mgmt.	34%	20%	7%	22%	17%
Learning effort was very high	10%	39%	10%	39%	2%
Also suitable for other application	22%	24%	39%	12%	2%
Needed a lot of external support	12%	29%	15%	39%	5%

Source: FD20 farmer survey 2024 (N=41).

As mentioned earlier, 'discontinuance' is equivalent with a passive rejection of an innovation and presents the decision to unuse a technology after having previously adopted it. This results either through replacement or through disenchantment. The FD20 is currently the most common representative of its type in Europe and has also been on the market the longest. Due to the established sales structure for the FD20, switching to other automated systems is not easy and is also associated with higher establishment and training costs. Reversibility is also limited, making it difficult to return to previous production systems, as there is currently no second-hand market for used equipment, which may change in the future, though. Although the reliability of the robot is not yet rated as optimal (only 24% of respondents are completely satisfied), and users still have to contend with frequent system error notification (42% of the respondents receive more than 20 notifications per year), discontinuance is not recognisable among the Bavarian organic sugar beet farmers: The sample comprises eleven farmers who are already using the FD20 in their fourth year of sugar beet production and 14 who have been using the robot for at least three years. However, due to the Bavarian funding program (BaySL Digital), there is a mandatory commitment period of five years to use the FD20 on the funded farm. Nonetheless, the information provided by the early adopters in this survey indicates that the robot seems to become established in organic sugar beet production.

Conclusions

Assigning the survey results in the context of the well-established innovation-decision-process of Rogers provides valuable insights into the experiences of early adopters and offer important guidance for the future development of field robots. According to the survey results, the Bavarian early adopters of the Farmdroid FD20 were generally satisfied with the use of the robot in the first years of implementation, but also communicated several points for technical improvements. The advancement of field robot technology can be more effectively driven by actively involving farmers in the development and optimisation process. Early adopters, in particular, make significant contributions through their commitment and practical experience, helping to refine and improve innovative technologies. In line with Rogers' description of early adopters as a specific group within the adoption curve, first-time users of the market-ready robot show openness to new ideas and are pragmatic and enthusiastic about potential benefits of the innovation. They are very interested in the technology itself, know how to implement the technology with external help and carry out their own modifications to the robot and the tools themselves. In this way, early adopters qualify as sources of information and opinion leaders, which in turn are important for subsequent potential users of the FD20 in the first stages of the innovation-decision process. Ultimately, for potential users of robotic weed control, learning from the experiences of early adopters is crucial to assessing factors like economic efficiency, weed management quality and technology reliability for their own operations. However, another of Rogers' conclusions in his theory, namely that later adopters are more likely to discontinue innovations than early adopters, has yet to be confirmed. Although the surveyed farmers were all beneficiaries of the Bavarian funding programme and therefore committed to the robot for five years, the results of the survey show no significant dissatisfaction with the FD20 and a low probability of discontinuance.

In contrast to the conventional production sector, where manual weed control does not play a major role, the use of the FD20 in organic cultivation is somewhat of a success story. According to official statistics, there are around 356 farms with organic sugar beet production in Bavaria. This indicates that around 18% of these farms are already equipped with a robot. The high adoption rate highlights the promising potential of robots to transform organic farming practices and support more sustainable, efficient crop management in the region. It can be assumed that further innovative systems will enter the market in the coming years, emphasising the importance of better understanding the mechanism of innovation with respect to autonomous agricultural technology.

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